

PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

MEASURING THE SURFACE TENSION OF NASAL MEDICINAL PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

The surface tension of nasal medicinal products affects their rate of evaporation, interaction with a mucous membrane of the respiratory tract and the rate of spreading over biological surfaces. The surface tension of the studied vasoconstrictive nasal pharmaceutical preparations was within the normal range of 37.94 – 42.14 mN/m. A comparative analysis of the obtained data was carried out and the influence of this physicochemical parameter on the distribution of medicinal products over the mucous membrane and their potential pharmacological efficacy was substantiated.

Keywords: Surface tension, nasal drops, mucous membrane, pharmacokinetics.

Introduction. The deterioration of the global environmental situation, the spread of viral infections, and, as a consequence, the increasing incidence of upper respiratory tract diseases lead to a growing demand for nasal medicinal products [1, 7]. Nasal drops are a dosage form intended for local administration that provides a rapid decongestant and vasoconstrictive effect by stimulating α -adrenergic receptors [8, 11]. They reduce hyperemia, swelling of the mucous membrane, and decrease exudation, thereby facilitating nasal breathing in cases of rhinitis. Nasal drops may be vasoconstrictive (0.05 % – 0.1 %), moisturizing (0.65 %), or antiallergic, and are typically supplied in 5–10 mL vials [8].

Nasal drops are one of the simplest and most convenient systems for nasal drug delivery. The main requirements for this dosage form include safety (absence of toxicity), stability of active substances, ease of dosing and compliance with established standards. Nasal drops should be sterile (or have a low level of microbial contamination), possess a pH close to physiological values (5.5 – 6.5) and be isotonic in order to prevent irritation of the mucous membrane [8, 11].

According to the literature, nasal drops deposit human serum albumin in the nostrils more effectively than nasal sprays [3]. Drops spread more widely throughout the nasal cavity and reach the posterior part of the nasal cavity, where mucociliary clearance is more active, which ensures faster elimination of the drug from the cavity [3, 11]. The main drawback of this system is insufficient dosing accuracy; therefore, nasal drops may not be suitable for prescription medications.

Liquid drug delivery systems undergo thorough experimental testing that extends beyond pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic studies, including assessments of pH, viscosity, density, stability, isotonicity and other parameters. One parameter that is often overlooked is surface tension at the air–liquid interface. This is more readily understood for oral or parenteral

liquid dosage forms, as they rapidly disperse within the body's physiological aqueous environments [5]. However, for nasal preparations, which have significantly greater interaction with air, this parameter may have a considerably greater impact on drug delivery efficiency.

According to the literature, surface tension has become one of the key parameters used to characterize liquid properties in the development of new pharmaceutical dosage forms, particularly for improving drug stability and bioavailability [3, 10]. It has been established that surface tension, as a pharmacological criterion, it is suitable for evaluating drug solubility, pKa, blood–brain barrier penetration, oral in vivo efficacy and drug release [3–4, 6]. Different routes of administration require liquid dosage forms to remain within a specific surface tension range. For example, oral dosage forms typically exhibit a surface tension range of 36.6 to 64.7 mN/m, whereas nasal preparations have a range of 30.3 to 44.9 mN/m [3].

The surface tension of nasal preparations influences their rate of evaporation, interaction with the mucous membrane of the respiratory tract and the rate of spreading over biological surfaces [3, 10]. To minimize irritation, it could be expected that liquid formulations would generally mimic the natural surface tension of the specific site of administration, thereby maximizing interaction. Thus, determining surface tension is appropriate at the stage of development and quality control of nasal drops, as it directly affects their efficacy, safety and ease of use.

The objective of the study was the experimental determination and analysis of the surface tension of liquid nasal drops using a stalagmometer.

Materials and Methods. Five vasoconstrictive nasal drops were selected for the studying of surface tension: “Vibrocil”, “Rinazolin”, “Farmazolin”, “Nazivin”, and “Naphthyzin” [9]. The surface tension of the

investigated preparations was measured using a stalagmometer [3, 10]. The number of drops (n_0) formed during the outflow of distilled water (standard liquid) from the stalagmometer and the number of drops (n) for each nasal preparation were determined. Measurements were repeated three times and the average value of the number of drops was calculated. The density (ρ) of the studied solutions was determined using an areometer. The surface tension (σ) of the nasal drops was calculated using a formula (1) and expressed in mN/m:

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \frac{n_0 \cdot \rho}{n \cdot \rho_0} \quad (1)$$

The surface tension value of distilled water (σ_0) was taken from tabulated data at a temperature of $t = 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Results and Discussion. Vasoconstrictive nasal preparations are a group of medicinal products used locally to reduce swelling of the nasal mucosa and facilitate nasal breathing. They mainly belong to sympathomimetic agents and exert their effect through stimulation of α -adrenergic receptors in the blood vessels of the nasal mucosa, leading to vasoconstriction and a reduction in hyperemia and exudation [1, 7].

The main representatives of this group include derivatives of imidazoline and phenylethylamine, in particular xylometazoline, oxymetazoline, naphazoline and phenylephrine. Some of them, in addition to their vasoconstrictive effect, may exhibit additional properties such as moderate anti-inflammatory, antioxidant or antiallergic activity [7–8]. However, with prolonged or excessive use, the development of tachyphylaxis, drug-induced rhinitis and reduced drug efficacy is possible; therefore, their use should be limited in duration and carefully controlled [8].

For successful absorption of a nasal medicinal product, the active pharmaceutical ingredient must first

reach the absorptive barrier. In the nasal cavity, molecules must be absorbed by the epithelial membrane before being eliminated or degraded. In addition, controlling the release profile of the active pharmaceutical ingredient across barriers such as the mucus layer, epithelial layer, and capillary endothelium may be beneficial [6].

Determination the surface tension of nasal drops is a relevant and important physicochemical parameter, especially at the stages of their development and quality control. Surface tension influences the ability of droplets to spread over the nasal mucosa: if this value is high, the droplet poorly wets the nasal surface and may quickly run off before being absorbed. An optimal or lower surface tension ensures a more uniform distribution of nasal pharmaceutical preparations and better contact with the mucous membrane of the nasal cavity.

It was found that all investigated nasal medicinal products had a surface tension at the air–liquid interface lower than a surface tension of the fluid of a mucous membrane of the upper respiratory tract (Table 1). Under normal conditions, the surface tension of nasal mucous secretion is 35–45 mN/m [11]. The investigated surface tension values of nasal drops were as follows: “Vibrocil” – 41.89 mN/m, “Rinazolin” – 37.94 mN/m, “Farmazolin” – 42.14 mN/m, “Nazivin” – 39.70 mN/m, and “Naphthyzin” – 38.35 mN/m. The lower surface tension allows nasal drops to more easily wet the surface of the nasal mucosa and be uniformly adsorbed across it.

The lowest surface tension values were observed for the pharmaceutical preparations “Rinazolin” and “Naphthyzin”. However, this parameter did not exceed the acceptable range. This ensures easier spreading of nasal drops over the surface of the nasal cavity, thereby improving drug distribution and absorption. Nasal medicinal products with lower surface tension may provide potentially higher bioavailability.

Table 1.

Surface tension of the investigated nasal drops

Name of medicinal product	Active substance (dosage)	Pharmacological properties	Surface tension, mN/m
1	2	3	4
<i>Vibrocil</i>	dimetindene maleate (0.25 mg/mL), phenylephrine (2.5 mg/mL)	Phenylephrine belongs to sympathomimetic amines. It is used as a nasal decongestant with a moderate vasoconstrictive effect and selectively stimulates α_1 -adrenergic receptors of the cavernous venous tissue of the nasal mucosa. Dimetindene maleate, an H_1 -histamine receptor antagonist, exerts an antiallergic effect [9].	41.89
<i>Rinazolin</i>	oxymetazoline (0.5 mg/mL)	Oxymetazoline exerts a sympathomimetic and vasoconstrictive effect, reducing swelling of the nasal mucosa. It constricts blood vessels at the site of application, decreases swelling of the nasal and upper respiratory tract mucosa and reduces nasal discharge. The reduction of nasal mucosal edema promotes the restoration of aeration of the paranasal sinuses and the middle ear cavity, thereby preventing the development of bacterial complications [8].	37.94

Farmazolin	xylometazoline (1 mg/mL)	Xylometazoline is a sympathomimetic agent that acts on α -adrenergic receptors. Farmazolin causes constriction of nasal blood vessels, reducing swelling of the nasal mucosa and its paranasal sinuses, thereby improving nasal breathing in cases of nasal and sinus congestion. Due to its moisturizing component (sorbitol), the drug helps reduce dryness and irritation of the nasal mucosa [7–8].	42.14
Nazivin	oxymetazoline hydrochloride (0.5 mg/mL)	Oxymetazoline exerts a sympathomimetic and vasoconstrictive effect, relieving swelling of the nasal mucosa. Oxymetazoline also demonstrates antiviral, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, and antioxidant activity [8].	39.70
Naphthyzin	naphazoline (1 mg/mL)	Naphthyzin exerts a pronounced vasoconstrictive effect on peripheral blood vessels through its action on α -adrenergic receptors. When applied to mucous membranes, it reduces edema, hyperemia, and exudation, thereby facilitating nasal breathing in cases of rhinitis. Naphazoline promotes the opening and dilation of the outflow ducts of the paranasal sinuses and Eustachian tubes, improving secretion drainage and preventing bacterial colonization [9].	38.35

According to the experimental results, nasal drops “Farmazolin” and “Vibrocil” exhibit the highest surface tension values. This indicates that these medicinal products are characterized by relatively lower wetting ability, which may limit their uniform distribution over a nasal mucosa and reduce the contact area with the biological surface. The effectiveness of a drug is determined not only by its physicochemical properties but also by its composition, the concentration of active substances and its pharmacodynamic characteristics.

Conclusions. The surface tension of the investigated vasoconstrictive nasal drops ranged within the normal limits of 37.94 – 42.14 mN/m. The lowest values of this parameter were observed for the medicinal products “Rinazolin” and “Naphthyzin”. This contributes to increased bioavailability of active substances. Thus, the determination of surface tension is an important physicochemical parameter that influences drug distribution and its biopharmaceutical effectiveness.

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